

THE INFLUENCING FACTORS AND MECHANISMS OF CONTINUANCE INTENTION OF INDIVIDUAL USERS OF CLOUD NOTE

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Abstract

This research aims to understand the factors that affect the continuance intention of individual users can help Cloud Note service providers optimize their services and enhance their competitiveness. Based on Information System Success Theory (ISSM), a structural equation model was constructed to comprehensively consider system quality, service quality, switching cost, user habits, and satisfaction, and to analyze the factors influencing the continuance intention of individual users of Cloud Note. Statistical analysis software were used to analyze the data collected through the survey questionnaire. The results uncovers that service quality and system quality have a positive effect on satisfaction. System quality, switching cost, usage habits, and user satisfaction have a significant effect on the continuance intention of individual users of Cloud Note. User satisfaction has a mediating effect between system quality, service quality, and continuance intention, but the direct effect of service quality on continuance intention has not been tested. This research constructed a factor model for the continuance intention of individual users of Cloud Note based on ISSM, and provided a new research perspective for Cloud Note through empirical testing. But there was no in-depth interview on the user's true feelings.

Keywords: Cloud Note, Personal Users, ISSM, Continuance Intention.

1. INTRODUCTION

China's datasphere has expanded by about 14 times between 2018 and 2025, rapidly growing at an average annual growth rate of 30%. By 2025, China's data volume will become the world's largest (IDC, 2019). With the rapid development of the Internet, China's bandwidth has increased from KB to MB, terminals have moved from the PC era to the mobile era, and data volume has also entered the ZB era from GB. The amount of information people are exposed to every day is increasing exponentially. How to effectively and quickly find new information and convert it into knowledge is a problem that we have to face. Personal knowledge management can solve these problems (Wenfeng & Xiang, 2022). The use of tools plays a crucial role in personal knowledge management (Sudibjo et al., 2022). Cloud Note is a personal knowledge management tool that has emerged in recent years. It facilitates users to record information in various forms anytime, anywhere, and can quickly save webpage content. Cloud Note generally supports multi-platform clients, which can achieve information synchronization between clients and cloud servers (Xiaoling & Qingdong, 2018).

With the rapid popularization of mobile intelligent terminals and mobile internet, various types of Cloud Note have emerged one after another, and the development potential of China's Cloud Note market is enormous. However, compared to countries such as Europe and America, Chinese Cloud Note companies have not developed well: firstly, low awareness of payment and difficulty in commercialization. Secondly, the growth rate of mobile internet users has been decreasing year by year, the market

is approaching saturation, and users have entered the stage of stock competition. How to cultivate the market and open up the growth space of the personal user market for Cloud Note? At present, only by continuously exploring the value of existing users and paying attention to their continuous use may be the true long-term path for Chinese Cloud Note enterprises.

However, scholars currently mainly focus on Cloud Note products themselves and new technologies, and there is very little study on the initial usage intention of existing users (Coursaris et al., 2013; Gatwood et al., 2021), the study on continuance intention is blank. Therefore, this study takes ISSM as a guide to explore its influencing factors and path relationships, which helps to enhance the growth space of China's Cloud Note market and promote the development of the digital economy industry.

2. THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS AND MODEL CONSTRUCTION

2.1 Theoretical Basis - ISSM

DeLone and McLean (2003) improved the original Information System Success Model (D&M). The improved ISSM includes three independent variables: Service quality refers to the judgment of all service support provided by IS. System quality refers to evaluation of information system itself. Information quality related to the measurement of the output of information system. These three factors not only directly influence user satisfaction and willingness to use information systems, but also have an impact on user intention through satisfaction.

The improved ISSM not only maintains simplicity but also adapts better to the increasingly evolving environment and is widely used in various fields to evaluate whether a new system can bring practical benefits to people (Yi, 2019). However, this model only provides a comprehensive thinking framework. In practical research environments, specific research variables need to be selected according to local conditions (Xinyi et al., 2018). Cloud Note is a system tool that helps users collect and organize various information. The quality and service of the system are crucial, and are also one of the main differences between different Cloud Note systems. However, this study focuses on individual users of Cloud Note system, so when selecting independent variables, information quality was artificially removed. This is because the information in the Cloud Note system is customized by the user, and the quality of the information depends on the individual user.

2.2 Hypotheses development

2.2.1 Theoretical basis variables

The ISSM is a milestone achievement in the field of IS success research. In recent years, this model has been widely applied in user continuous use. When exploring the continuance intention of individual Cloud Note users, this study also recognizes the core concept of ISSM, and adopted DeLone and McLean (2003) definition of these variables. Meanwhile, seven hypotheses are proposed based on theory.

H1: System quality has a significant impact on the satisfaction of individual users of Cloud Note.

H2: System quality has a significant impact on the continuance intention of individual users of Cloud Note.

H3: Service quality has a significant impact on the satisfaction of individual users of Cloud Note.

H4: Service quality has a significant impact on the continuance intention of individual users of Cloud Note.

H5: Satisfaction significantly has a significant impact on the continuance intention of individual users of Cloud Note.

H6: Satisfaction serves as a mediating factor between system quality and continuous intention of individual users of Cloud Note.

H7: Satisfaction serves as a mediating factor between service quality and the continuance intention of individual users of Cloud Note.

2.2.2 Habits

Habit is a behavioral trend formed by an individual's past experiences that will automatically execute before issuing self-instructions. Limayem et al. (2007) argue that habit originates from the repeated use of behavior, which is an autonomous response to stimuli, and consider frequency and comprehensive use as factors that influence habit formation. Therefore, this research considers habit to be the degree to which users automatically use Cloud Note without judgment. Limayem et al. (2007) found in their research of sustained use by internet users that when users develop habits, they exhibit unconscious sustained use. Tam et al. (2020) pointed out that experienced users of information systems are more likely to form habits, which positively influence sustained intention. Chih et al. (2021) also found that the usage habits of cloud services positively influence the continuance intention. According to the above research, this study proposes a hypothesis:

H8: Usage habits have a significant impact on the continuance intention of individual Cloud Note users.

2.2.3 Switching cost

Switching cost refers to the time, money, and cognitive effort required for users to transfer from one service provider to another (Jidong & Xue, 2019). If the switching cost of using another service is high, users may still choose to continue using the current service (Zheng, 2019). The same applies to the continuous use of a specific information system by users. The higher the switching cost, the stronger the willingness to use the existing system (Yu, 2020). Based on the usage context of Cloud Note, this study defines switching cost as the time, money, effort, and other costs incurred by users when transitioning from using one Cloud Note system to using another or from Cloud Note to other personal knowledge management tools.

Jian (2020) found in his research on college students' continuous use of music Apps that switching cost positively affected their continuous intention. Jidong and Xue (2019) also found in their research on mobile social network information services that perceived switching cost has the most significant impact on the continuance intention. The research results of Yu (2020) on the influence on users' willingness to continue using mobile shopping apps confirm that switching cost has a positive impact on users' continuance intention, and increasing switching cost helps to enhance users' continuance intention. To determine the impact of switching cost on the continuance intention of individual Cloud Note users. According to the viewpoints of the scholars mentioned above, this research proposes a hypothesis:

H9: Switching cost significantly positively impact the continuance intention of individual users of Cloud Note.

2.3 Model construction

The continuance intention of information system is not only affected by systemic factors, but also by user usage habits and switching cost. Therefore, based on ISSM, this study integrates usage habits and switching cost to construct a factor model for the continuance intention of individual users of Cloud Note (Figure 1). This research model is composed of antecedent variables (system quality, service quality, usage habits, and switching cost), mediator variables (user satisfaction), and outcome variables (continuance intention).

Figure 1: Continuance intention model of individual users of Cloud Note

3. METHOD

3.1 Questionnaire Design

This study is based on mature scales and modifies measurement items in combination with the characteristics of Cloud Note system. The first part of the questionnaire adopts the Likert seven level scale to set measurement items for six variables: system quality, service quality, conversion cost, usage habits, user satisfaction, and willingness to continue adoption (see Table 1 for details). The second part is a survey of user basic information.

Table 1: Measurement Questions and Sources

Variable	Items	Source
system quality(SYQ)	The Cloud Note system runs stably and smoothly.	Peng (2018); Yungming (2021)
	The interface design of Cloud Note system is reasonable.	
	Rich functions of Cloud Note system.	
	Cloud Note system responds quickly.	
	Cloud Note can provide effective security to prevent unauthorized access.	
	Cloud Note System is Reliable.	
service quality(SQ)	There are relevant prompts on the Cloud Note system to facilitate my self-service.	Yifang (2016);

	When users require it, the Cloud Note system can provide personalized services.	Chunhui et al. (2021)
	The Cloud Note system is free or reasonably priced.	
	Cloud Note systems do not collect too much personal data and privacy.	
habit(HAB)	Using Cloud Note has become my habit.	Peng (2018); Yifang (2016)
	It was a no-brainer for me to use Cloud Note.	
	Using Cloud Note is a natural thing for me.	
	I have to use Cloud Note when Collecting and collating information.	
switching cost (SWC)	Switching to other Cloud Note software requires me to spend a lot of time and effort re familiarizing with its functions and operations.	Yunqiu (2021)
	Switching to other Cloud Note software, I'm not sure I'll get better service.	
	If I switch to other Cloud Note software, I may lose information that is important to me.	
	If I no longer use Cloud Note, I will lose a lot of Historical information collected and collated.	
Satisfaction (SAC)	I am satisfied with the capacity of Cloud Note.	Yungming (2022); Yu (2020)
	My experience utilizing Cloud Note has left me feeling quite delighted.	
	The features that Cloud Note offers have greatly pleased me.	
	My whole Cloud Note experience has been satisfactory.	
	Using Cloud Note is a smart choice, in my opinion.	
continuance intention (CON)	In the future, I'm willing to keep utilizing Cloud Note.	Yu (2020); Yungming (2019)
	In the future, I'll keep using Cloud Note.	
	In the future, I'll utilize Cloud Note a lot.	
	Rather of using any other programs, I want to stick with Cloud Note.	
	I'm willing to use more of Cloud Note's features.	

3.2 Questionnaire Survey

The individual Cloud Note users residing on the Chinese Mainland are the research's target population parameter.

The world's largest Chinese online communication platform, Baidu Tieba, provided the sampling framework for this study, which allowed researchers to find respondents who fit the aforementioned criteria. Six Tieba connected to Cloud Note were ultimately chosen as the sampling units for this study based on user behavior and timely updates. "Baidu Tieba" is primarily intended for users in China.

These people have used at least one Cloud Note software, which is highly consistent with the requirements of this study on target population factors. Six Tieba connected to Cloud Note basically cover multiple Cloud Note software with more users in the Chinese market. In this survey, 459 questionnaires were issued; of them, 59 were deemed ineligible since they had the same choice selected and the online response time was displayed as less than one minute.

A total of 400 valid surveys (87.0%) were gathered. In terms of scientific research ethics, this study follows the ethical principles of Bouma (2000) for investigation. Participants are informed that participation in the survey is entirely voluntary prior to it. The response is private and anonymous. In addition, let participants know that submitting completed surveys signifies their consent to participate in the study and that this data would only be utilized for academic purposes.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Descriptive statistical analysis

Among the respondents, 203 were males(50.7%), and 197 were female (49.3). The gender ratio structure is relatively balanced; In terms of age, 200 people aged 30 and below (50%), 160 people aged 30-40 (including 40) (40%), 39 people aged 40-50 (9.7%), and 1 person aged 50 and above (0.3%); In terms of education, there are 7 individuals with a high school degree or below (1.8%), 366 individuals with a university degree (91.4%), and 27 individuals with a graduate degree or above (6.8%). People with greater education and younger ages are more mentally active and willing to accept and use Cloud Note, according to the respondents' personal characteristics. Regarding experience with utilization, , 37 people (9.3%) have been using it for less than 1 year, 152 people (38%) have been using it for 1-3 years, 148 people (37%) have been using it for 3-5 years, and 63 people (5.7%) have been using it for more than 5 years; 61 users (15.3%) are located in the western area, 80 users (20%) are in the center inland area, and 259 users (64.7%) are in the eastern coastal area. The user's location sample size more closely matches the state of the region's economic development.

4.2 Reliability and Validity Analysis

Cronbach's Alpha was utilized in this study to assess the scale's reliability. According to the test results (Table 2), all variables have Cronbach's α values over 0.8, all CITC values are above 0.5, and all item correlations are above 0.4. All variables meet the test criteria recommended by Churchill (1979) and Hair et al. (1998). indicating high reliability of the measurement model. This suggests that there is excellent reliability in the measurement model.

Table 2: Reliability test results

	Item correlation						Reliability	
	SYQ1	SYQ2	SYQ3	SYQ4	SYQ5	SYQ6	CITC	Cronbach's α
SYQ1	1.000						.746	.915
SYQ2	.642	1.000					.755	
SYQ3	.617	.659	1.000				.763	
SYQ4	.668	.610	.669	1.000			.774	
SYQ5	.652	.646	.618	.661	1.000		.770	
SYQ6	.582	.637	.659	.654	.671	1.000	.759	
	SQ1	SQ2	SQ3	SQ4				
SQ1	1.000						.690	.869
SQ2	.563	1.000					.722	
SQ3	.625	.634	1.000				.726	
SQ4	.623	.676	.624	1.000			.747	
	HAB1	HAB2	HAB3	HAB4				
HAB1	1.000						.689	.831
HAB2	.589	1.000					.647	
HAB3	.550	.519	1.000				.641	
HAB4	.575	.525	.549	1.000			.656	
	SWC1	SWC2	SWC3	SWC4				
SWC1	1.000						.660	.835
SWC2	.677	1.000					.771	
SWC3	.408	.547	1.000				.548	
SWC4	.592	.664	.482	1.000			.692	
	SAC1	SAC2	SAC3	SAC4	SAC5			
SAC1	1.000						.627	.838
SAC2	.469	1.000					.627	

SAC3	.516	.508	1.000				.658	
SAC4	.498	.495	.540	1.000			.638	
SAC5	.518	.529	.519	.495	1.000		.650	
	CON1	CON2	CON3	CON4	CON5			
CON1	1.000						.739	.888
CON2	.715	1.000					.851	
CON3	.654	.829	1.000				.808	
CON4	.541	.588	.536	1.000			.612	
CON5	.570	.630	.637	.452	1.000		.674	

The measuring items' discriminant and convergent validity were examined in this study using confirmatory factor analysis. According to Table 3, all items have standardized factor loadings that are greater than 0.6 and significant at the 0.001 level; all variables have composition reliability (CR) values greater than 0.8 and AVE values greater than 0.5, which are in line with expert recommendations (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). This suggests that the convergent validity of the scale is good.

Table 3: Convergence validity and fitness of measurement model

	Item	Parameter significance estimation				factor loading	Item reliability	composite reliability	convergent validity	Fitness of Measurement model
		Unstd	S.E.	t	P	std	smc	CR	AVE	
SYQ	SYQ1	1.000				.786	.618	.915	.643	x ² /df=1.652, GFI=0.988 AGFI=0.972, CFI=0.995 RMSEA=0.04
	SYQ2	1.062	.062	17.087	***	.794	.630			
	SYQ3	1.069	.062	17.366	***	.804	.646			
	SYQ4	1.047	.059	17.705	***	.817	.667			
	SYQ5	1.139	.065	17.563	***	.811	.658			
	SYQ6	1.069	.062	17.257	***	.800	.640			
SQ	SQ1	1.000				.751	.564	.869	.625	x ² /df=2.176, GFI=0.995, AGFI=0.974, CFI=0.996, RMSEA=0.054
	SQ2	1.122	.073	15.302	***	.797	.635			
	SQ3	1.066	.070	15.165	***	.789	.623			
	SQ4	1.123	.071	15.734	***	.823	.677			
HAB	HAB1	1.000				.785	.616	.831	.552	x ² /df=0.98, GFI=0.998, AGFI=0.988, CFI=1.0, RMSEA=0
	HAB2	.921	.068	13.611	***	.731	.534			
	HAB3	.940	.070	13.372	***	.717	.514			
	HAB4	.987	.072	13.714	***	.737	.543			
SWC	SWC1	1.000				.758	.575	.842	.576	x ² /df=3.051, GFI=0.993, AGFI=0.964, CFI=0.994, RMSEA=0.072
	SWC2	1.163	.071	16.300	***	.886	.785			
	SWC3	.856	.074	11.618	***	.604	.365			
	SWC4	1.016	.068	14.863	***	.762	.581			
SAC	SAC1	1.000				.698	.487	.838	.509	x ² /df =0.661, GFI =0.997, AGFI=0.99, CFI =1.0, RMSEA=0
	SAC2	1.010	.084	12.070	***	.698	.487			
	SAC3	1.065	.085	12.595	***	.735	.540			
	SAC4	.996	.081	12.254	***	.711	.506			
	SAC5	1.032	.083	12.433	***	.724	.524			
CON	CON1	1.000				.768	.590	.891	.626	x ² /df=3.202, GFI=0.984, AGFI=0.953, CFI=0.991, RMSEA=0.074
	CON2	1.175	.059	20.067	***	.930	.865			
	CON3	1.168	.061	19.137	***	.884	.781			
	CON4	.574	.044	12.958	***	.634	.402			
	CON5	.656	.045	14.506	***	.700	.490			

Additionally, the arithmetic square root of each variable's AVE value is used to calculate discriminant validity. According to the findings, the questionnaire has strong discriminant validity because the arithmetic square root of AVE was more than or comparable to the correlation coefficient between this variable and other variables (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Table 4: Test results of discriminant validity

	AVE	CON	SAC	SWC	SQ	SYQ	HAB
CON	.626	.791					
SAC	.509	.577	.713				
SWC	.576	.434	.250	.759			
SQ	.625	.388	.738	.163	.791		
SYQ	.643	.511	.618	.192	.458	.802	
HAB	.552	.520	.348	.158	.254	.276	.743

4.3 Fitness of measurement model and structural model

The model fitness needs to satisfy a certain requirement in order to guarantee the fitness between the sample data and the structural equation model. In order to evaluate the fitness between the measurement model and the structural model, this study creates a structural equation model and chooses five fitness indicators that are frequently used by academics.

Table 3 displays the measuring model's fitness. All measurement models had χ^2/df values between 0 and 5, RMSEA values less than 0.08, and CFI, GFI, and AGFI values around or equal to 1. The measuring models' fitness is good, and all indicators have achieved an acceptable level.

While this is going on, Figure 2's various fitting indicators ($\chi^2/df=1.363<3$; CFI=0.98, GFI=0.926, AGFI=0.911, all greater than 0.9; RMSEA=0.03<0.08) show that the structural model has good overall fitness and can be used for research-related hypothesis testing. These indicators also meet the standards recommended by experts (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

4.4 Path coefficient test

This study conducts path analysis on structural models using maximum likelihood estimation method. This study tested the research hypothesis at a significance level of 0.05. From Table 5 and Figure 2, it can be seen that the system quality and service quality of Cloud Note have a significant positive impact on user satisfaction, assuming that H1 and H3 are valid; The quality of the Cloud Note system has a positive impact on user continuance intention, assuming H2 valid; However, if H4 is false, then service quality cannot directly influence users' intentions to stick with a product; on the other hand, if H5, H8, and H9 are true, then user satisfaction, usage patterns, and switching costs all positively influence users' intentions to stick with a product.

Table 5: Test results of path coefficients

Hypothesis	path	Standardized path coefficient	S.E.	C.R.	P	Result
H1	SYQ→SAC	.356	.047	6.813	***	accept
H2	SYQ→CON	.194	.046	3.332	***	accept
H3	SQ→SAC	.579	.053	9.358	***	accept
H4	SQ→CON	-.086	.056	-1.164	.244	not accept
H5	SAC→CON	.345	.079	3.855	***	accept
H8	HAB→CON	.340	.038	6.853	***	accept
H9	SWC→CON	.285	.041	6.186	***	accept

Figure 2: Path Analysis Results of Structural Equation Model

4.5 Mediation effect test

This study uses the Bootstrap macro program to repeatedly extract 5000 times to test the mediating effect. According to Table 7, all mediation pathways do not include 0 at the 95% confidence interval, and the mediation effects of both mediation pathways are significant. It is assumed that both H6 and H7 are valid. Further from Table 6, it can be seen that the direct effect between system quality and continuance intention is significant ($p < 0.05$), suggesting that the relationship between system quality and continuing intention is somewhat mediated by user satisfaction. The direct effect between service quality and continuance intention is not significant ($p > 0.05$), indicating that user satisfaction plays a complete mediating role between service quality and continuance intention.

Table 6: Direct Effect Analysis Results

DV	IV	coeff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
SAC	constant	.931	.190	4.893	.000	.557	1.305
	SYQ	.302	.035	8.526	.000	.232	.372
	SQ	.414	.033	12.613	.000	.349	.478
CON	constant	2.757	.174	15.850	.000	2.415	3.099
	SAC	.260	.045	5.839	.000	.173	.348
	SYQ	.198	.034	5.794	.000	.131	.265
	SQ	.027	.034	.776	.438	-.041	.095

Table 7: Indirect Effect Analysis Results

	Effect	BootSE	BootLLCI	BootULCI
SYQ--SAC--CON	.079	.020	.044	.125
SQ--SAC--CON	.108	.024	.066	.160

5. DISCUSSION

5.1 The influencing factors of personal user satisfaction with Cloud Note

This study takes system quality and service quality as antecedents of personal user satisfaction with Cloud Note, and proposes two research hypotheses (H1 and H3) based on this. The empirical results indicate that both H1 and H3 are supported by data, indicating that system quality and service quality play important roles in user satisfaction. This conclusion is consistent with previous research on knowledge banking systems (AbdelKader & Sayed, 2022), This suggests that raising the system and service quality can boost Cloud Note user satisfaction.

5.2 Factors influencing the continuance intention of individual cloud note taking users

Based on ISSM, this study thoroughly examines how usage patterns, switching costs, system and service quality, and individual Cloud Note users' intentions to stick around are all affected. Based on this, five research hypotheses (H2, H4, H5, H8, and H9) are proposed. The empirical results indicate that H2, H5, H8, and H9 are all supported by data, and the above four conclusions are consistent with previous research on user continuance intention (Chih et al., 2021; Jian, 2020). However, H4 has not received data support, and the direct effect of service quality on user continuance intention is not significant. This study is consistent with the research results of scholars on the continuance intention of mobile government users (Zhongruen, 2022). The aforementioned findings suggest that users' intentions to stick with a system are significantly influenced by its quality, their usage patterns, and the cost of moving. Further analysis of the impact of four factors on the continuance intention of individual Cloud Note users reveals that both user satisfaction and usage habits have significant and comparable effects on continuance intention ($\beta=0.34$, $p<0.001$), Next is the switching cost ($\beta=0.29$, $p<0.001$) and system quality ($\beta=0.19$, $p<0.001$), therefore, improving the continuance intention of individual users of Cloud Note can be achieved by improving system quality, increasing switching cost, and cultivating user usage habits.

5.3 Discussion on the mediating role of user satisfaction

This study focuses on Cloud Note and explores the mediating mechanism of user satisfaction between system quality, service quality, and continuance intention. The empirical results indicate that user satisfaction has a mediating effect between them, and H6 and H7 are supported by empirical data, which is consistent with the results in ISSM. System quality is the most important factor for users to use Cloud Note system. With the development of information technology, the demand for Cloud Note functions from users is increasing day by day. If the system has comprehensive functions, reasonable interface design, and stable and smooth operation, users will form a high degree of satisfaction and have a high possibility of using it again. On the contrary, users may give up using it again. Therefore, Cloud Note providers should attach importance to the quality of Cloud Note system, improve corresponding system functions to improve user satisfaction, and thereby enhance their continuance intention.

Users select the Cloud Note system concurrently according to their demands, and service performance evaluations will be formed during use. If users believe that Cloud Note system has high cost-effectiveness, can meet personalized needs, and can

provide timely feedback on issues, it will form a high level of satisfaction. On the contrary, users are clearly not satisfied. Based on user experience, users will make corresponding evaluations and decide whether to use it again. Through research on Cloud Note system, it has been found that there is a certain relationship between user evaluation of the service quality of Cloud Note system and satisfaction. The higher the service quality of Cloud Note system, the higher the user satisfaction. Therefore, in the process of designing Cloud Note system, Cloud Note providers should pay attention to service effectiveness, improve service quality through improving corresponding service functions, innovating service forms, providing personalized and professional services, and thereby enhancing the continuance intention of individual Cloud Note users.

6. CONCLUSION

This study is based on ISSM, integrating switching cost and usage habits, exploring the factors influencing the continuance intention of individual Cloud Note users. The aim is to provide reference for Cloud Note service providers to improve user stickiness and improve Cloud Note system, while verifying the applicability of ISSM in Cloud Note environments. Although the research model constructed in this study has passed empirical testing, the psychological variability of users is difficult to quantify, and the influencing factors are complex and diverse. However, due to limitations such as time and energy, this study only focuses on the above factors. Therefore, further research can be conducted from the following two aspects in the future: Selecting influencing factors from multiple perspectives, enriching the research model, and conducting in-depth interviews with the latent variables involved, so that the variables can better reflect the actual situation of individual users of Cloud Note. Consider exploring using multiple theories or replacing other more suitable theories in order to obtain more accurate conclusions.

Data availability statement

The authors do not have permission to share data.

Institutional review board statement

Not applicable.

Informed consent statement

Not applicable.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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